

Energy-dispersive X-ray mapping in SEM and STEM

T. Walther

Dept. of Electronic & Electrical Engn., University of Sheffield, Sheffield S1 3JD, UK

E-mail: t.walther@sheffield.ac.uk

Keywords: X-ray spectroscopy, X-ray mapping, In(Al)GaAs quantum wells and dots

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS) is a standard method for chemical analysis in electron beam instruments such as scanning electron microscopes (SEM) or transmission electron microscopes (TEM). While a related paper discusses ways of quantifying more reliably single X-ray spectra, this contribution focuses on the spatial resolution of X-ray maps obtained using full EDX spectrum images that contain complete X-ray spectra at each data point.

In an SEM, bulk samples are investigated that can be easily prepared. Spatial resolution is often poor because the electron beam can penetrate deep into the sample, and due to multiple elastic–inelastic scattering the interaction volume will be large. Typical lateral widths of the effective probe are in the range of 100nm–1 μ m. The spatial resolution can only be improved in three ways:

- i) analysing the near-surface regions where the interaction volume is still relatively small (near the stalk or stem of the pear-shaped interaction volume, cf. figure 1 [1]),
- ii) reducing the electron beam voltage to reduce the interaction volume (which however will also reduce the number of X-rays produced as well as restrict the line types that can be studied, due to the Duane-Hunt limit) or
- iii) reducing the sample thickness to cut off the largest part of the interaction volume in the bulk, effectively employing thin TEM samples in SEM [2].

In a TEM, electron transparent thin foil samples are investigated, which reduces the interaction volume significantly and thereby improves the spatial resolution, but the number of X-rays produced is thereby reduced also, and large solid-state X-ray detectors can often not be brought close enough to the point where the electron beam hits the sample because the latter sits within a narrow, cone-shaped pole-piece of the objective lens. Hence, count numbers are often low and maps quite noisy. There are again a number of important points:

- a) While there have been examples of atomic lattice resolved X-ray maps at 0.4nm [3] and 0.8nm [4] resolution, the pseudo-coloured maps presented do not actually state contrast levels, and line scans across the structures often turn out to be far too noisy to assess spatial resolution properly. Usually, atomic resolution will only be possible at certain foil thicknesses, and multi-slice simulations will be needed to assure which atomic columns the X-ray signals actually come from [5].
- b) Lattice resolution is only possible along zone-axis orientations which, similar to two-beam conditions, should generally be avoided for quantification because of channelling effects.
- c) Maps from thin foil samples are not easily interpretable in terms of atomic concentrations because of surface effects (1nm oxide layers on top and below a 40nm thin sample can change results by 5%) and local thickness variations (so only ratios of intensities will be meaningful but will be even noisier than raw maps [6]).

Figure 1. Monte Carlo simulation of electron interaction with 10nm InGaAs on GaAs. 5nm electron beam at 4kV (insert at top right) and 15kV. The latter is 8x larger! red: backscattered, blue: absorbed electrons

Figure 2. Secondary electron image with coloured X-ray map of central $(0.8\mu\text{m})^2$ region of thin InAs layer on surface of GaAs at 15kV (nom. thickness: 0.45nm, exp. value: $0.81\pm 0.24\text{nm}$) [1]

Figure 3. 200kV ADF STEM image (a) of capped InGaAs quantum dots in top view and X-ray maps of As K (b), In L and Ga K as composite map (c), showing lack of overgrowth around islands despite capping by nominally 8nm GaAs. [7]

Figure 4. 200kV ADF STEM image of In(Al)GaAs quantum wells in cross-section (a), X-ray map of Al K signal (b); map of Ga K, Al K, In L intensities as composite RGB map (c). The weak Al signal within the upper InGaAs layer corresponds to 0.3 monolayers ($< 0.1\text{nm}$!) [8].

Acknowledgements

The author acknowledges Mark Hopkinson (University of Sheffield) and Emil-Mihai Pavelescu (National Institute for R&D in Microtechnologies, Bucharest) for provision of samples.

References

1. T. Walther, *Nanomaterials* **12**:13 (2022) 2220
2. H. Demers, N. Brodusch and R. Gauvin, *Microsc. Microanal.* **23**: S1 (2017) 1044-1045
3. A.J. D'Alfonso, B. Freitag, D. Klenov and L.J. Allen, *Phys. Rev. B* **81** (2010) 100101R
4. H.S. von Harrach et al., Proc EMAG2009, Sheffield, *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* **241** (2010) 012015
5. B.D. Forbes et al., *Phys. Rev. B* **86** (2012) 024108
6. T. Walther, J. Bai and X. Wang, *J. Microsc.* **272**:2 (2018) 111-122
7. S.L. Liew et al., *Springer Procs. Phys.* **120** (2007) 259-262
8. T. Walther et al., *Semicond. Sci. Technol.* **35** (2020) 084001